

On the Dynamics of a Dual-flap Out-of-Phase Floating Oscillating Surge Wave Energy Converter

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Abstract:

The oscillating surge wave energy converter (OSWEC) captures wave energy by oscillating under waves and demonstrates superior performance compared to most other types of wave energy converters (WECs). However, existing OSWECs are primarily designed for nearshore bottom-hinged deployment. To expand OSWEC deployment from nearshore to deep water, we investigate a dual-flap out-of-phase floating oscillating surge wave energy converter (FOSWEC). Deep water deployment offers higher wave power density and reduced visibility of WECs as well as less regulation concerns. The proposed FOSWEC comprises a floating platform and two pivoting flaps positioned at a distance of approximately half the wavelength to achieve out-of-phase motion, minimize frame motion, and decrease mooring load. In this study, we introduce the detailed multi-body dynamic modeling method for this dual-flap FOSWEC concept, elucidate its operating principles, and compare it with a single-flap FOSWEC of similar dimensions. Simulation results demonstrate that the proposed dual-flap design significantly reduces platform horizontal motion, leading to reduced mooring load. We provide a comprehensive evaluation of different design parameters' influence on FOSWEC performance, including mooring line stiffness, power takeoff damping, incident wave direction, and flap distance. To assess system performance experimentally, we designed, fabricated, and tested a 1:10 scaled prototype in the wave tank, following the Froude scaling law. Experimental results, validated against modeling outcomes, affirm the desired out-of-phase phenomenon. With the validated model, we present a case study of a 100kW FOSWEC intended for the PacWave South test site.

Fig.1 Dual-flap Floating Oscillating Surge Wave Energy Converter Concept

Fig.2 Wave Tank Setup of a 1:10 Scaled Model